

You Made Me Realize

Liann Camille Davalos Perez, LPT. MAEd.
Educator. Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia

I am a sucker for romance, I must admit,
 Fond of shared glances across the halls or whispers underneath blankets.
 Yet I once hated it,
 Planning to journey through this life alone.

Until you came.

Not as a knight in shining armor,
 but confident and gentle,
 steady hands,
 a presence that felt like home and a confidant.

You made me realize that love is patient:
 waiting while I finish my curls,
 watching me take the last bites long after you've finished yours,
 Slowing your steps, thus, we can walk side by side.

You made me realize that love is kind:
 No shouts and raised voice, only calm resolve,
 Conversations are centered on respect,
 silence that feels full instead of suffocating.

You made me realize that love is generous:
 no keeping tabs, neither mine nor yours.
 Sacrifices and gifts given freely,
 because wanting the best for each other comes naturally.

You made me realize that love is a choice:
 choosing to call me every day,
 telling me how content you feel to have me,
 especially on days when anger lingers, and it would be easier not to.

You made me realize that love feels easy,
 no doubts, no hesitation, just certainty.
 Not unforgiving with myself, not at war with you.
 Like a Sunday morning by the lake, peaceful and quiet.

You made me realize that love is not grand.
 It lives in knowing how I like my coffee,
 switching seats to my comfort,
 watching musicals with me, though you prefer action or sci-fi.

It lives in lowering the volume when the noise overwhelms me,
 preparing my sweets while I work,
 waiting for hours just to pick me up at the airport,
 and surprising me with flowers, just because.

To name all the things you've made me realize might take a lifetime.
 For your presence has made my life new.
 Such a blessing in a human form
 The one I will always be grateful for, through and through.

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